

CoARA Action Plan 2026-2029

Saxion

Overall Characterisation

Saxion University of Applied Sciences is one of the largest institutions of higher education in the Netherlands, with close to 27,000 students 2500 staff members. Saxion University has a rich history - its roots can be traced back to 1875. A merger of two educational institutions, the Hogeschool Enschede and Hogeschool IJsselland, paved the way for Saxion University in its present form in 1998. This merger enabled Saxion to build further on its strong position in Dutch higher education and since then Saxion University has come to be recognised as an important centre of expertise at a regional, national and international level.

As a University of Applied Sciences, Saxion has 27 research groups in the field of health and wellbeing, smart industry, built environment, economics and education. These groups carry out applied research based on authentic questions from the professional practice-based research, based on questions from the professional field, consisting of small and medium enterprises, schools, hospitals, municipalities and other entities. Saxion is committed to advancing a research evaluation culture that fits with the nature of practice-based research and is in line with the impact areas of the Dutch Sector Protocol for Practice-Based Research. The CoARA commitments recognise the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. Endorsing the CoARA principles is therefore a logical step for a Dutch University of Applied Sciences and for Saxion in particular, being among the first Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands to sign the agreement.

This Action Plan reflects the priorities that Saxion has identified based on an analysis of each of the ten commitments. Saxion is actively involved in the Dutch CoARA chapter and aims to contribute to the transformation of research assessment towards more diverse research output that has impact on the professional practice and society in general, on education and on the advancement of knowledge.

Organisation type

Public University of Applied Sciences

Date of joining CoARA

2024

Due date of first action plan

2026

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CoARA Commitment 1

Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

Purpose: This commitment will broaden recognition of the diverse practices, activities and careers in research, considering the specific nature of research disciplines and other research endeavours.

Scope: Changes in assessment practices should enable recognition of the broad diversity of:

- valuable contributions that researchers make to science and for the benefit of society, including diverse outputs beyond journal publications and irrespective of the language in which they are communicated;

- practices that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and the inclusiveness of research and the research process including peer review, teamwork and collaboration;
- activities including teaching, leadership, supervision, training and mentoring.

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

Saxion uses the Sector Protocol for Practice-Based Research of the Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences for the evaluation of research. This Protocol uses four standards:

- *Standard 1:* The research unit has a relevant, ambitious and challenging research profile and research programme.
- *Standard 2:* The research unit makes transparent what its contribution is to the development of professional practice and society at large, of education, and of the research domain.
- *Standard 3:* The research unit's research complies with the standards applicable in the field with regard to conducting research.
- *Standard 4:* The way in which the unit is organised, the deployment of people and resources, and the internal and external partnerships, networks and relationships, make it possible to achieve the research profile.

Standard 2 is aimed at the impact of research in three areas: the professional practice and society at large, education and the professionalisation of the teaching staff of the institution and advancement of knowledge. Hence, the current assessment practice has already taken into account the contributions to science and society and contributions to education. As research groups must comply with the Netherlands Code of Research Integrity, Standard 3 of the Sector Protocol, the practices that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and the inclusiveness of research are also part of research assessment. Research Units are the object of evaluation and are evaluated every six years. The six-year period coincides with the validity of the Sector Protocol.

In our quality assurance policies, no specific norms or thresholds for indicators are established. This is a purposeful policy, as the reflection and discussion on the performance on the indicators is more meaningful in our research assessment than the achievement of specific norms. Furthermore, as the developmental stages of our research groups and units are varying, standardised norms or thresholds do not contribute to a contextualised reflection and may lead to a 'race to the top' that does not contribute to real impact of research. Joint reflection and elaboration of relevant actions are more important in our quality assurance than specific quantitative performance on indicators.

As to the Saxion careers in research, the job classification system consists of seven research functions:

1. Junior research assistant
2. Research assistant
3. Junior researcher
4. Researcher
5. Senior researcher
6. Associate professor
7. Professor

A working group of the Dutch Association of Universities of Applied Research is currently studying the possibilities for research career paths for UAS researchers.

As far as assessment of individual researchers, there is no standardised measurement of individual research output. Researchers are evaluated in the general cycle that

includes a planning meeting, a progress meeting and an end-of-year assessment meeting. The nature of the meetings is mainly qualitative.

Saxion is committed to Open Science and research integrity. We strongly encourage our researchers to consider the benefits of adopting open research approaches with respect to all elements of the research process, and to incorporate such additional steps as are appropriate to their research project. This may include, for example, the pre-registration of research, the reuse of Open data, the use of Open source code and software, Open analysis, Open reporting through the use of open lab notebooks and processes, the Open publishing of data and software, Open Peer-review, Open Access publishing of outputs, Open Educational Resources, the use of persistent identifiers and Open metadata.

Recognising the nature of practice-oriented research, we adhere to the principle of 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary,' providing justification for any limitations. It is recognised that it may not be appropriate to undertake all open activities with every type of research, especially non-publicly funded research, where there may be IP issues, or research involving sensitive data of various kinds, where GDPR legislation or trusted research principles may apply. There is also a need to take a proportional approach to what is published; for example, it may be more appropriate to make algorithms or software open source rather than a full suite of data resulting from them if this would adequately support reproducibility concerns. In order to facilitate this, Saxion employs support staff specialised in copyright and licensing, data management, privacy and GDPR, Open source and software, metadata and publishing and offer an increasing number of services aimed at facilitating Open Science Practices. Open science practices are further supported through policies including Open Access Publishing including budget for Author Processing Costs, Data (Re)use, the use of Persistent Identifiers.

Part of our triannual dialogue on research integrity with all research groups, is on promoting open data/open science.

Planned activities

2026

Refinement of representation of indicators for research assessment in dashboard. Data quality OK and the best input for internal reflection and discussion on what is relevant to make impact with practice bases research.

At national level, the Dutch Association of Universities of Applied Sciences strives for a joint approach to the definition of research careers. As research is relatively young at universities of applied sciences (< 30 years), most careers paths are currently based on teaching. Research careers as a focus in HR is relatively new. Saxion aligns with the guidelines, advice and/or frameworks from the Association and will not focus on development of Saxion specific research careers.

2027

Open Science:

1. *Infrastructure 2027*: Saxion will implement a new repository. The use of SURF Sharekit will better facilitate the opening of both research outputs and metadata. It will also allow better use of Persistent identifiers such as the ORCID, DOI and RAiD. This will also facilitate better participation in the national platform Publinova.
2. *Policy 2026*: In accordance with the Open Science movement, Saxion will implement an Open Science Statement, summarising their stance on Open Science principles. Reflecting the maturity of our Open Science policies, our current policies on Open Access Publishing, Data Reuse, and use of Persistent Identifiers, as well as those areas currently in development such as Open Research Software, will be harmonised into a comprehensive Open Science Policy.

3. *Commitment (2026)*: In alignment with the Dutch Association of Universities of Applied Sciences, Saxion will sign the Barcelona Declaration, exemplifying its commitment to Open metadata.

FAIR open data and FAIR open research software:

1. Professionalisation

- As part of the Digital Competence Center for Practice Oriented Research (DCC-PO), Saxion will further strengthen its expertise in the areas of Open Research Data and Open Research Software. To support this objective continuous knowledge development initiatives will be established to ensure alignment with national and international FAIR data management standards and best practices.
- A data management plan tool will be selected/developed and implemented to facilitate structured and compliant research data management.
- FAIR data management training sessions are and will be developed and delivered to researchers.

2. Infrastructure

To enhance sustainable storage, sharing, and publication of research data and software:

- DataverseNL will be implemented as the institutional platform for the storage, sharing, and publication of research data upon project completion. The platform will enable researchers to publish datasets and make them openly accessible where appropriate.
- A solution for the storage, management, and publication of FAIR research software will be identified and implemented.
- A Research Software Management Policy will be developed and formalized to support sustainable, transparent, and reusable research software practices.

CoARA Commitment 2

Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

Purpose: This commitment will enable the move towards research assessment criteria that focus primarily on quality, while recognising that responsible use of quantitative indicators can support assessment where meaningful and relevant, which is context dependent.

Scope: Research assessment should rely primarily on qualitative assessment for which peer review is central, supported by responsibly used quantitative indicators where appropriate. Peer review is the most robust method known for assessing quality and has the advantage that it is in the hands of the research community. It is important that peer review processes are designed to meet the fundamental principles of rigor and transparency: expert assessment, transparency, impartiality, appropriateness, confidentiality, integrity and ethical considerations, gender, equality and diversity. To address the biases and imperfections to which any method is prone, the research community re-assesses and improves peer review practices regularly. Revised, or potentially new, criteria, tools

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

Saxion uses a dashboard for performance on quality assurance indicators. The research dashboard, (Kwaliteitskaart Onderzoek Saxion – KOS), consists of ten indicators related to the four standards of the Sector Protocol for Practice-Based Research.

Standard 1

- The percentage of project volume contributing to the focus areas of Saxion as part of the total project volume
- The percentage of project volume contributing to the regional strategic agenda of Saxion as part of the total project volume

Standard 2

- The in kind and in cash contributions of external partners compared the total project volume
- The contribution to education through different educational activities (guest lecture, supervision of assignments, supervision of thesis, etc.)
- The percentage number of hours dedicated to research as part of the total number of hours available

Standard 3

- The result of the integrity dialogue
- The results of the peer reviews

Standard 4

- The primary, secondary and tertiary funding sources
- Amount of fte and number of people
- Presence of a quality system

The performance on each one of the indicators is reflected upon in an online environment called the 'Reflection tool' that is filled out and discussed extensively with professors, associate professors and presidents of schools. In this tool, several questions are answered, and professors reflect on the current state of the performance on the indicators, their evaluation of the current situation and the possible actions to be planned. The outcomes of the reflections are shared within the research unit and with the president of the school. Peer review is one of the indicators and all groups are required to organise at least two peer review sessions per year.

Planned activities

The Sector Protocol not only requires a basic set of indicators but also sets of optional indicators related to the four standards. With the optional indicators, each unit can profile itself and show its ambition in specific directions. The optional indicators have not been included in the dashboard so far and will be visualised in 2026 to complete the overview of indicators in the dashboard.

CoARA Commitment 3

Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

Purpose: This commitment will reduce the dominance of a narrow set of quantitative journal- and publication-based metrics.

Scope: Inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics in research assessment should be abandoned. In particular, this means moving away from using metrics like the Journal Impact Factor (JIF), Article Influence Score (AIS) and h-index as proxies for quality and impact. 'Inappropriate uses' include: relying exclusively on author-based metrics (e.g. counting papers, patents, citations, grants, etc.) to assess quality and/or impact;

Actions 2026-2029

Current activities

This commitment is already fully functioning. Journal and publication-based metrics do not play a large role in the assessment of practice-based research. They are not part of the basic indicators of the Saxion dashboard KOS. Conditions for impact are measured in a different way and directly related to the required impact fields of the Dutch Sector Protocol. Publications are archived in the Saxion Research Repository and by some of the research units used as an optional indicator to give additional insights in the impact on the knowledge domain. It is important to highlight that in practice-based research professional publications, e.g. in magazines of sector organisation, are also highly relevant as these publications are read directly by the professional field and therefore more likely to have a direct impact on the professional field.

Timeframe

Planned activities

N. A.

CoARA Commitment 4

Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Purpose: This commitment will help avoid that metrics used by international rankings, which are inappropriate for assessing researchers, trickle down to research and researcher assessment. It will help the research community and research organisations regain the autonomy to shape assessment practices, rather than having to abide by criteria and methodologies set by external commercial companies. This could include retaining control over ranking methodologies and data.

Scope: Recognising that the international rankings most often referred to by research organisations are currently not ‘fair and responsible’, the criteria these rankings use should not trickle down to the evaluation of individual researchers, research teams and research units. Research organisations should also be mindful that public communication (e.g. the active advertising of an institution’s rank) can contribute to the perception that research quality conflates with ranking positions.

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

Saxion recognises that rankings and comparative tools are part of the higher education landscape and are used, for example, in external communication and student information. However, Saxion does not use rankings as a basis for research assessment as rankings do not adequately capture the nature and impact of practice-based research as conducted at Universities of Applied Sciences.

Research assessment at Saxion is grounded in the principles of practice-based research and in keeping with the Dutch Sector Protocol for Practice-Based Research. Our Research Dashboard (Kwaliteitskaart Onderzoek Saxion – KOS) provides a structured framework for monitoring and reflecting on research quality and impact. It includes indicators on societal relevance, collaboration with external partners, contribution to education, research integrity, peer review, and funding diversity. These indicators are qualitatively interpreted through structured reflection and dialogue within research groups and between professors, associate professors and institutional leadership. Therefore, rankings are neither embedded in internal evaluation processes, nor do they inform decision-making on research performance or career progression.

Planned activities

Saxion will maintain autonomy over its research assessment practices and contribute to a broader shift towards responsible, qualitative and impact-oriented evaluation in line with CoARA principles. To do this, Saxion will uphold alternative approaches that reflect the nature of practice-based research.

Specifically, we will:

- Promote awareness within the Saxion and the broader UAS community that rankings do not adequately reflect the value of practice-based research and its contribution to professional practice and regional ecosystems;
- Uphold the use of qualitative, context-sensitive evaluation methods within the KOS framework (peer review, dialogue, reporting on societal impact etc);
- Ensure that external communication about institutional performance remains balanced and contextualized, avoiding the conflation of research quality with ranking positions and highlighting instead concrete examples of impact, collaboration and innovation.

CoARA Commitment 5

Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to

Purpose: This commitment will ensure that organisations allocate the necessary resources, whether in the form of budget or staff capacity, to improve research assessment practices within their agreed timeframe.

Scope: Resource allocation by assessment authorities and research funding and performing organisations is a necessary condition for reforming assessment practices. Resources should be allocated as is needed for each organisation to achieve the changes that will enable adherence to the Principles and to implement the Commitments. This includes resources to:

- implement changes in research assessment, including planning and progress monitoring;
- raise awareness among all actors;
- educate, train and support researchers and any other staff involved in assessment, including peer-reviewers and assessors; and
- support the necessary infrastructure such as tools and services for the transparent collection and processing of data on research assessment practices.

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

Resource allocation and institutional support

- Saxion allocates an **annual professional development budget** from central resources, distributed across organisational units.
- Each unit develops an **annual professionalisation plan** as part of its yearly planning cycle, identifying training needs and allocating budget for staff development.
- Budgets can be used for internal training via the Saxion Corporate Academy or external training providers.

Training and capacity building

- The **Saxion Corporate Academy** offers a structured training portfolio covering professional development, personal development, and employee vitality.
- The training offer is organised around **eight thematic areas, including research**, ensuring support for staff involved in research and research-related activities.
- **Training formats** include workshops, courses, e-learning modules, and knowledge clips, enabling flexible participation.

Tailored support and learning on the job

- Where needed, **customised support** (learning-on-the-job) can be provided to staff on specific topics related to their work.

Continuous updating of training offer

- The **training portfolio is regularly evaluated and updated** based on organisational training needs, changes in internal policies or working methods, and developments in national or international legislation and regulations.

Infrastructure and information support

- Saxion maintains a **dedicated research intranet site** that provides guidance and documentation for researchers and staff, including:
 - manuals for research software tools,
 - institutional procedures and policies,
 - relevant legal and regulatory information.

Planned activities

N. A.

CoARA Commitment 6

Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes

6.1 CRITERIA FOR UNITS AND INSTITUTIONS

With the direct involvement of research organisations and researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria for assessing research units and research performing organisations, while promoting interoperability

Purpose: This commitment will ensure that national / regional / organisational authorities and evaluation agencies review and, where needed, develop criteria for the assessment of research performing units and organisations, in accordance with the Principles. It will foster the responsible use of metrics in assessing research performing units and organisations and help to prevent contradictions or incompatibilities between the assessment of research, researchers and research performing organisations. It will also safeguard the interoperability of adapted or newly developed assessment processes.

Scope: Criteria for the assessment of research performing units and organisations, including universities, research centres, and research infrastructures, should be reviewed and adapted, and new criteria developed where needed, based on evidence. This should be done in close collaboration with assessors and those that will be assessed, including research organisations and researchers. The changes should increase the ability to assess quality by enabling recognition of all contributions to quality research by research units and institutions. Such recognition includes that of early sharing of data and results, open collaboration, teamwork, and consideration of contributions to the research ecosystem, knowledge generation and scientific, technological, economic, cultural and societal impact. National / regional / organisational authorities and evaluation agencies should coordinate to ensure their methodologies and processes are interoperable, while simultaneously respecting the necessary adaptation to each context.

Actions 2026-2029

Current activities

The evaluation of research units happens according to the Sector Protocol of the Dutch Association of Universities of Applied Sciences. The protocol has a limited set of indicators that is compulsory. For Standard 4, 'The way in which the unit is organised, the deployment of people and resources, and the internal and external partnerships, networks and relationships, make it possible to achieve the research profile' there are two compulsory indicators: 1) the allocated funding – including direct university funding, funding by funding national and international agencies and contract research – and 2) the staff involved in research, including academic and non-academic staff. All remaining other indicators for research assessment are determined by each institution. Saxion has developed a set of ten basic indicators as described above for Commitment 2. Each research unit has also determined a set of additional indicators, as prescribed by the Sector Protocol and described in the Saxion quality assurance policies. Under Commitment 2, the set of basic indicators is described. As already stated, research is assessed at the level of research group and research units, not at the level of the individual researcher.

Planned activities

The current Sector Protocol is valid till 2028. The Dutch Association of Universities of Applied Sciences will evaluate and adapt the Sector Protocol for the following six-year period 2029-2034, taking the CoARA commitments into account. The association is involved in the CoARA National Chapter and is therefore committed to the principles. In the course of 2027, the revised Sector Protocol will be presented.

At Saxion level, the new Sector Protocol, together with the experiences of the current protocol and the process and results of the external and internal evaluations, will result in revised quality assurance policies.

Timeframe

2027

2027

CoARA Commitment 6

Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and process

6.2 CRITERIA FOR PROJECTS AND RESEARCHERS

With the direct involvement of researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria, tools and processes for the assessment of research projects, research teams and researchers that are adapted to their context of application

Purpose: This commitment will enable recognition of the diverse research activities and practices through the revision and development of assessment criteria, tools, and processes. It will ensure that organisations review their processes and make tangible changes by developing existing or new assessment approaches, individually or in collaboration with others, in accordance with the Principles.

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

The current indicators for the assessment of research quality are based on the sector protocol and developed in collaboration with researchers and quality assurance staff. Input from the research community was collected during the development phase. A first evaluation has already taken place after the first series of external evaluations. A revision of the dashboard and a refinement of the indicators have been implemented. The data quality of the dashboard is of major importance and has continuous attention.

Planned activities

As the current indicators recognise a wide range of research activities, related to the three impact areas, no specific activities are planned for this commitment, apart from the regular evaluations of the dashboard, reflection tool and revision of the quality assurance policies.

CoARA Commitment 7.

Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Purpose: This commitment will ensure that organisations raise awareness of the reform among all actors. It will ensure that organisations transparently communicate the criteria, tools and processes used for research assessment and train researchers and assessors in their use.

Scope: Without widespread awareness of the reform and training of those assessed and, crucially, assessors, progress will be slow – if not impossible. Organisations should be clear and transparent about assessment processes and the tools and criteria they use. They should make guidance on their assessment approaches openly available and train those involved in the assessment process. They should allow those assessed to have access to the criteria, data and reviews or deliberation outcomes used in their assessment within the limits of confidentiality. Particular attention should be paid to raising awareness among researchers at all career stages.

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

Saxion as a University of Applied Sciences commits to monitoring and evaluating the implementation of reforms in research assessment and to communicating these developments transparently across the organisation. To foster understanding, engagement and collective learning, Saxion actively involves its research community in the transition towards a more qualitative, diverse and impact-oriented approach to research assessment, in line with the principles of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment.

Planned activities

2028

During the period 2026–2028, Saxion will implement a set of actions aimed at strengthening engagement, communication, training and monitoring within the research community. A communication plan will be developed to inform professors, associate professors and other researchers, research support staff and their managers about the reform of research assessment and Saxion’s CoARA commitments, and to actively involve them in this transition.

Key activities include:

- **Strengthening internal networks** within academies, strategic research themes, Centres of Expertise and research groups to facilitate information sharing and the exchange of experiences related to the implementation of research assessment reforms.
- **Using internal communication channels** to inform the research community about CoARA principles and their implementation at Saxion, including the internal 'Research' theme site, news updates via the MijnSaxion platform and the internal newsletter.
- **Organising training and dialogue**, including training modules within the Saxion Academy learning environment, to support researchers, professors, research support staff and managers in understanding and applying the new principles for research assessment. Existing consultation structures, such as the research support coordination meeting, will also be used to share knowledge and exchange experiences.
- **Ensuring transparency and external communication** by sharing information on CoARA principles, the institutional action plan and implementation progress via the research web environment on saxion.nl/research and through internal communication channels.
- **Increasing visibility and awareness** through articles and practice-based stories developed with the internal editorial board and PR channels, highlighting examples of responsible research assessment and societal impact.

Insights and feedback gathered through these communication and training activities will be used to monitor progress and further refine the implementation of research assessment reforms at Saxion.

CoARA Commitment 8

Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

Purpose: This commitment will ensure organisations exchange and make use of information for mutual learning. It will help avoid fragmentation, contribute to the coherence of assessment practices between organisations, and enable researcher mobility. It also will allow those further ahead to share approaches and lessons learned, to benefit those who have further to go on their reform journey.

Scope: While respecting each other's autonomy, organisations should share practices and experiences to facilitate mutual learning. This exchange should include contributing to the development of guidance and common approaches in order.

Actions 2026-2029

Current activities

Saxion has already been involved in national and international networks that also focus on research assessment. The Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences has several network groups that facilitate mutual learning, like the policy network (HON) and the quality assurance network ((LNKO). In these network, experiences and best practices are shared and lessons are learned. At conferences like the European Quality Assurance Forum international networks are created and used for exchange of experiences and best practices.

The Dutch Chapter of CoARA is also an important means to mutually learn from other institutions within the Netherlands and enhance the exchange between research universities and universities of applied sciences.

Planned activities

As planned activities, Saxion will remain active in the CoARA National Chapter, currently as one of the frontrunners among universities of applied sciences. Saxion will

Timeframe

Continuous

also aim to be closely connected to international networks such as EQAF to benefit from practices elsewhere.

CoARA Commitment 9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments

Purpose: This commitment will ensure organisations update one another on the progress made. It will foster careful self-reflection and monitoring of their own adherence to the Principles and progress towards meeting the Commitments.

Scope: Demonstrating progress made towards implementing the Commitments and adherence to the Principles is an important part of this initiative. Organisations should commit to regularly update each other and their communities on their adherence and progress. This process involves being open to scrutiny from their own communities, sharing successes as well as challenges, and communicating their experiences to facilitate collective progress.

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

Saxion has a small project group committed to the adherence to the CoARA principles and implementation of this CoARA Action Plan. The project group aligns all stakeholders within Saxion and is committed to sharing progress, challenges and experiences with the Saxion research community.

Planned activities

The first step is to publish the Saxion CoARA Action Plan on Zenodo and on the Saxion thematic research intranet. Progress will also be published on the internal research intranet. The Action Plan and the progress will also be shared on the Saxion website on a dedicated CoARA page.

2029

CoARA Commitment 10

Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

Purpose: This commitment will ensure that assessment approach decisions are evidence informed. It will help organisations reflect on their own processes, gain understanding about whether assessment practices achieve the desired goals and engage in evolutive assessment based on new evidence as it becomes available. It will also help to ensure control and ownership of research assessment data by the research community.

Scope: Growing evidence shows that current assessment processes that rely on publication- and journal-based metrics are prone to multiple biases. As approaches using more qualitative research assessment are piloted by several organisations (e.g. narrative and evidence-based CVs, new assessment frameworks and indicators), it is important to evaluate and monitor their impact based on evidence and rigorous methods.

Actions 2026-2029

Timeframe

Current activities

We recognise that we currently do not evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and state-of-the-art in research on research.

Planned activities

We will engage more in evidence-based assessment by evaluation of our current HR assessment practices and sector protocol evaluation instruments:

1. Relate the assessment of individual researchers to research performance, based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, both for:
 - Selection of researchers
 - Assessment of researchers
2. Strengthen the assessment of research groups and research units based on research on research